

**RESULTADO DA SELEÇÃO DE ARTIGOS APÓS A APLICAÇÃO DA ETAPA 7 DA
METHODI ORDINATIO**

N *	Artigos selecionados	JCR **	Cit ***	Ano	Ind ****
1	Organizational Transparency: Conceptualizations, Conditions, and Consequences	5,30	473	2019	71,577
2	Conditions for innovation in public sector organizations	7,50	421	2017	48,785
3	Enhancing environmental information transparency through corporate social responsibility reporting regulation	12,50	162	2021	38,413
4	Corporate Governance and the Audit Process	3,20	1142	2002	34,587
5	An Exploratory Study Based on a Questionnaire Concerning Green and Sustainable Finance, Corporate Social Responsibility, and Performance: Evidence from the Romanian Business Environment	0,95	172	2019	28,572
6	PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION DIGITALIZATION AND CORRUPTION IN THE EU MEMBER STATES. A COMPARATIVE AND CORRELATIVE RESEARCH ANALYSIS	1,00	78	2022	26,501
7	The dimensional structure of transparency: A construct validation of transparency as disclosure, clarity, and accuracy in organizations	4,50	102	2021	26,405
8	Do cultural differences impact ethical issues? Exploring the relationship between national culture and quality of code of ethics	5,90	100	2021	26,006
9	How to deal with corruption? Examining the roles of e-government maturity, government administrative effectiveness, and virtual social networks diffusion	20,10	99	2021	25,820
10	A comparative study of anti-corruption practice disclosure among Malaysian and Indonesian Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) best practice companies	9,80	242	2016	25,210
11	Institutional quality, corruption, and impartiality: the role of process and outcome for citizen trust in public administration in 173 European regions	3,30	72	2022	25,003
12	Assessing Government Transparency: An Interpretive Framework	3,20	171	2018	24,378
13	Coercive Pressures and Anti-corruption Reporting: The Case of ASEAN Countries	5,90	90	2021	24,006
14	Corporate Governance in China: A Meta-Analysis	7,00	160	2018	23,007
15	Exploring transparency: a new framework for responsible business management	4,10	215	2016	22,504
16	Board age and corporate financial fraud: An interactionist view	7,40	154	2018	22,257
17	A Scoping Review on Perception-Based Definitions and Measurements of Corruption	1,30	25	2024	21,501
18	Reputational risk as a logic of organizing in late modernity	4,90	467	2009	21,475
19	Does corporate integrity culture matter to corporate social responsibility? Evidence from China	9,80	96	2020	21,010
20	Corporate integrity culture on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance	8,30	24	2024	21,008
21	A risk perspective on human resource management: A review and	8,20	197	2016	20,708

	directions for future research				
22	An Eye for Artificial Intelligence: Insights Into the Governance of Artificial Intelligence and Vision for Future Research	5,30	49	2022	19,255
23	Corporate corruption prevention, sustainable governance and legislation: First exploratory evidence from the Italian scenario	9,80	104	2019	18,867
24	Digitalization and prevention of corruption: Opportunities and risks - Some evidence from the Italian university system	12,50	18	2024	18,013
25	Alternative Governance and Corporate Financial Fraud in Transition Economies: Evidence From China	9,30	97	2019	17,866
26	Corruption as a perverse Innovation: The dark side of digitalization and corruption in international business	10,50	42	2022	17,511
27	Role of integrity system, internal control system and leadership practices on the accountability practices in the public sectors of Malaysia	2,90	94	2019	17,431
28	Public Sector Strategies in Curbing Corruption: A Review of the Literature	1,60	41	2022	17,252
29	Organizational risk culture: A literature review on dimensions, assessment, value relevance, and improvement levers	7,50	16	2024	17,008
30	A sustainable governance model to prevent corporate corruption: Integrating anticorruption practices, corporate strategy and business processes	12,50	71	2020	16,846
31	Introduction of a Corporate Security Risk Management System: The Experience of Poland	0,95	39	2022	16,751
32	Influence of Ethical Position on Whistleblowing Behaviour: Do Preferred Channels in Private and Public Sectors Differ?	5,90	102	2018	15,756
33	A risk management perspective on CSR and the marginal cost of debt: empirical evidence from Europe	7,80	48	2021	15,608
34	Assessment of ISO 9001: 2015 implementation: focus on risk management approach requirements compliance in an automotive company	3,60	46	2021	15,204
35	E-procurement and firm corruption to secure public contracts: The moderating role of governance institutions and supranational support	10,50	32	2022	15,011
36	A comparative analysis of Indian and Chinese FDI into Africa: The role of governance and alliances	10,50	31	2022	14,761
37	Ethos is Destiny: Organizational Values and Compliance in Corporate Governance	5,90	57	2020	14,506
38	Cleaning house before hosting new guests: A political path dependence model of political connection adaptation in the aftermath of anticorruption shocks	6,50	42	2021	14,407
39	Code of Ethics: A Stratified Vehicle for Compliance	5,90	131	2016	14,106
40	From Compliance to Progress: A Sensemaking Perspective on the Governance of Corruption	4,90	17	2023	13,672
41	Corporate governance reforms, societal trust, and corporate financial policies	7,20	9	2024	13,507
42	The use of internal control systems and codes of conduct as anti-corruption practices: evidence from Vietnamese firms	2,40	33	2021	12,602

43	Institutions and corruption relationship: Evidence from African countries	5,90	7	2024	12,506
44	Geographic Clustering of Corruption in the United States	5,90	32	2021	12,406
45	Compliance and resistance: How performance measures make and unmake universities	3,30	13	2023	12,337
46	Developing country firms and the challenge of corruption: Do company commitments mirror the quality of national-level institutions?	10,50	74	2018	12,261
47	Fighting Against Corruption: Does Anti-corruption Training Make Any Difference?	5,90	57	2019	12,149
48	The likelihood of widespread accounting manipulation within an emerging economy	3,20	30	2021	12,003
49	Accounting conservatism and corporate governance: evidence from India	3,00	30	2021	12,003
50	Corporate governance, internal audit function and accountability in statutory corporations	3,00	72	2018	12,003
51	Corruption Propensity and Mitigation at Different Phases of Infrastructure Development	1,00	6	2024	12,001
52	Corporate governance and cost of capital in OECD countries	4,30	40	2020	11,671
53	Bribing for Public Service: What Drives the Service Users?	1,80	11	2023	11,668
54	Democratizing Corporate Governance: Compensating for the Democratic Deficit of Corporate Political Activity and Corporate Citizenship	5,30	176	2013	11,544
55	Trust Deficit and Anti-corruption Initiatives	5,90	39	2020	11,506
56	Impact of Fraud Risk Assessment on Good Corporate Governance: Case of Public Listed Companies in Oman	1,20	38	2020	11,335
57	Corporate governance and accounting conservatism in Islamic banks	2,20	50	2019	11,145
58	Mapping Corruption Risks in Public Procurement: Uncovering Improvement Opportunities and Strengthening Controls	2,20	50	2019	11,145
59	Organizational Ethics, Individual Ethics, and Ethical Intentions in International Decision-Making	5,90	257	2010	11,068
60	Climate change adaptation narratives: Linking climate knowledge and future thinking	3,00	47	2019	10,717
61	Does Meritocracy Produce Desirable Outcomes for Public Organizations? Results of a Worldwide Expert Survey from 149 Nations	1,30	8	2023	10,668
62	Employee fraud and misconduct: empirical evidence from a telecommunication company	1,60	61	2018	10,627
63	Risk-based prioritization method for planning and allocation of resources in public sector	3,80	14	2022	10,504
64	Artificial intelligence capabilities, dynamic capabilities and organizational creativity: contributing factors to the United Arab Emirates Government's organizational performance	1,80	3	2024	10,502
65	How to deal with corruption? Examining the roles of e-government maturity, government administrative effectiveness, and virtual social networks diffusion	3,40	22	2021	10,403

66	Competency Management in Bureaucratic Organizations: Evidence from the Polish Public Administration	3,30	22	2021	10,403
67	Does stakeholder engagement affect corruption risk management?	1,30	74	2017	10,224
68	Beyond Unidimensional Measurement of Corruption	2,00	185	2012	10,216
69	Corporate governance mechanisms and their impact on company performance: A structural equation model analysis	5,90	2	2024	10,006
70	Do Wealth Managers Understand Codes of Conduct and Their Ethical Dilemmas? Lessons from an Online Survey	5,90	20	2021	10,006
71	Compliance Dynamism: Capturing the Polynormative and Situational Nature of Business Responses to Law	4,50	90	2016	10,005
72	Does bribery have a negative impact on firm performance? A firm-level analysis across 132 developing countries	3,30	2	2024	10,003
73	Fortifying Uzbekistan's integrity landscape: Harnessing India's tech-driven anti-corruption strategies	1,30	2	2024	10,001
74	Exploring the Attitudes of Kuwait's Residents Toward the Role of Corruption and Anti-Corruption Entities (Nazaha) in Kuwait	1,30	2	2024	10,001
INCLUÍDOS					
1	Corporate governance in islamic financial institutions	-	458	-	-
2	Corporate Governance, Risk Management, and the Financial Crisis: An Information Processing View	-	203	-	-
3	Auditors' consideration of corporate governance and management control philosophy in preplanning and planning judgments	-	393	-	-
4	The thinning of administrative institutions in the Hollow State	-	200	-	-

Legenda:

Nº*: Ordem de classificação dos artigos

JCR**: Fator de impacto da revista, obtido no *Journal Citation Reports*.

Cit***: Número de citações do artigo.

Ind****: Pontuação calculada no método *InOrdinatio*.